

Composition and Stability of Thorium(IV)-1(*o*-arsonophenyl-azo)-2-naphthol 3,6-Disulphonate (Thoron) Chelate

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Spectrophotometric studies on the composition and stability of the chelate formed between thorium and 1(*o*-arsonophenylazo)-2-naphthol 3,6-disulphonate (thoron) have been made at pH 3.0. The chelate is red in colour with λ_{max} at 515 m μ . The composition, as determined by different methods, is 1:2 (metal:chelating agent). The chelate is stable between pH 1.0 and 6.5. The values of log *K*, as determined by two different methods, are 9.4 ± 0.3 and 9.8 ± 0.2 respectively at pH 3.0 and at 25°.

Although a considerable amount of work has been done on the chromogenic properties of Thoron¹, the results on the composition and stability of the thorium chelate are conflicting²⁻⁴. We have undertaken a detailed investigation of metal chelates of thoron and the present communication deals with thorium-thoron system.

EXPERIMENTAL

A solution of thoron (B.D.H. laboratory reagent) was prepared by dissolving a known amount in doubly distilled, CO₂-free water. A stock solution of thorium chloride was prepared by dissolving thorium chloride (B.D.H. AnalaR) in doubly distilled, CO₂-free water and the solution was standardised gravimetrically.

Absorbance and pH measurements were made as reported earlier⁵. The same methods, as adopted earlier⁵, were followed to establish the composition of the chelate and for evaluating its stability constant.⁶

Table I shows the value of log *K* at pH 3.0 ± 0.2 , as determined by two different methods^{6,7}.

TABLE I
Stability constants of the chelate.

Method employed,	pH.	Log <i>K</i> .	ΔG° at 25° (kcal.)
Method of Dey <i>et al.</i> ⁷	3.0	9.40 ± 0.30	-13.0 ± 0.4
Mole-ratio method ⁶	3.0	9.80 ± 0.20	-13.0 ± 0.3

1. Kuznetsov, *Doklady Akad. Nauk., S. S. R.*, 1945, 50, 233.
2. Adamovich and Rutman, *Khor'K'ov. Gosudarst., Univ. im. A.M. Gor'Kogo*, 1954, 54; *Anal. Abst.*, 1950, 3, 2695; Clinch, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1956, 14, 162; Grimaldi and Fletcher, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 27, 1461.
3. Palmer, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 19, 458.
4. Byrd and Ockenden, U. K. Atomic Energy Authority, Ind. Group Hdq. RDB(W), 1955, 29, 5246; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 148.
5. Sangal *et al.*, *this issue*, p. 275.
6. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
7. Mukherji and Dey, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314.

In the method of Dey *et al.*⁷, the concentration of the chelate can be calculated by the following procedure. In an equilibrium of the type involving metal ion and a chelating agent in the ratio of 1:2 (as has been found in the system)

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where x is the concentration of the chelate at equilibrium and a and b respectively are the initial concentrations of the metal ion and the chelating agent. Taking two concentrations of the reagents, *i.e.*, two values of a and b where absorbance is the same, the value of x will also be the same. Hence

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a'-x)(b'-2x)^2} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$4x^2[(a+b)-(a'+b')] + x[b'^2-b^2+4(a'b'-ab)] + (ab^2-a'b'^2) = 0$$

$$x = \frac{-[b'^2-b^2+4(a'b'-ab)] \pm \sqrt{[b'^2-b^2+4(a'b'-ab)]^2 - 16[(a+b)-(a'+b')](ab^2-a'b'^2)}}{8[(a+b)-(a'+b')]}$$

FIG. 1. Composition of equimol. solns. at 540 m μ
($p=1$; $pH 3.0 \pm 0.2$).

Curve A: $c=1.00 \times 10^{-4}M$. Curve B: $c=0.80 \times 10^{-4}M$.
Curve C: $c=0.67 \times 10^{-4}M$.

FIG. 2. Composition by slope-ratio method
at $pH 3.0 \pm 0.2$.

A: 540 m μ . B: 550 m μ .
10 ml excess component ($2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$) + x ml
variable component ($0.83 \times 10^{-4}M$) + (10-x) ml H_2O .

Knowing the value of x in equation (1), the value of K can be calculated.

Sengal and Dey⁸ found that thoron behaved as a colloidal electrolyte and therefore very dilute solutions of the order $10^{-4}M$ were employed in these investigations.

The results obtained by following the method of Vosburgh *et al*⁹, indicate clearly that only one chelate having the λ_{max} at 515 $m\mu$ is formed under the conditions of study.

DISCUSSION

Stoichiometry of the Components

The composition of the chelate was established by the aforementioned methods at pH 3.0, using absorbance measurements. Fig. 1 summarises the results on the composition of the chelate using the continued variation method. In the legends, c represents the concentration of thorium chloride and p , the ratio c'/c , c' being the concentration of thoron. This composition is further corroborated by the mole-ratio method (Fig. 3) and slope-ratio method (Fig. 2).

FIG. 3. Composition by mole-ratio method at 540 $m\mu$. (pH 3.0 $\pm$ 0.3).
A: $c = 1.00 \times 10^{-4}M$. B: $c = 0.83 \times 10^{-4}M$.

The chelate is stable between pH 4.0 and 6.5 where the λ_{max} remains at 515 $m\mu$.

Some tentative suggestions for the position of the chelate ring may be made. It is well known¹⁰ that the donor properties of the azo group are weak, but azo compounds, which contain a strong donor group in a position *ortho* to the azo group, form very stable chelate rings. In thoron, there are the hydroxy group and an arsonic group in *ortho* posi-

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1980,

10. Bailar, "Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds", Reinhold, New York, 1956, pp. 74, 764-760.

tions to the azo group, which make it suited as a chelating agent. Both these groups are also capable of linking the metal ion by removal of a proton. Thus the structure (I) is suggested for the chelate.

As the chelate has been studied at pH 3.0, the sulphonic groups do not ionise and it may be expected that thorium-thoron chelate is neutral which is confirmed by passing the chelate through the ion-exchange resins. Neither Amberlite IR-45 or IR-120 (B.D.H. AnalaR) adsorb the chelate.

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